

Surrogate-assisted optimization for decision-making in lithium-ion battery manufacturing

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1 An insight into digital twins and surrogate modelling

In modern manufacturing systems, digital twins (DTs) have emerged as transformative enablers of smart, adaptive, and data-rich production. A digital twin continuously synchronizes real-time data from physical assets (*e.g.*, machines, sensors, and operators) with a virtual counterpart that mirrors the dynamic behavior of the production system. Such capabilities are particularly crucial in lithium-ion battery production, a process characterized by multi-stage workflows, nonlinear process dependencies, and tight interrelations between quality, energy efficiency, and time. Within this context, digital twins provide a virtual environment for testing parameter adjustments, anticipating defects, and minimizing downtime and contributing directly to the Zero-Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) paradigm [1]. This vision is also central to the European BATTwin¹ project, which develops a multilevel digital twin platform to enhance sustainability and defect reduction in Li-ion battery gigafactories across Europe.

Despite their potential, high-fidelity digital twins often suffer from significant computational cost and complexity. Each simulation can require large-scale numerical computation, limiting their ability to respond in real time or adapt to rapidly changing production conditions. As manufacturing moves toward data-driven, adaptive scheduling and online optimization, these constraints become critical bottlenecks. This limitation has driven growing interest in surrogate modeling; a strategy where simplified or data-driven models approximate the behavior of high-fidelity simulations. Surrogates, built using methods such as Gaussian processes and neural networks, can replicate system responses with drastically lower computational demand. This approach enables fast what-if analyses, uncertainty quantification, and iterative optimization, effectively extending the applicability of digital twins from offline design tools to real-time, closed-loop control systems [2].

The substitution of digital twins with surrogate modeling represents a promising frontier for intelligent and sustainable manufacturing. By embedding lightweight surrogate models directly into the optimization framework, it becomes possible to achieve both high computational efficiency and a faithful approximation of physical behavior. This integration enables the optimization engine to rapidly explore alternative process strategies or control decisions while still maintaining a realistic representation of system constraints and dynamics. In the case of Li-ion battery production, such a hybrid system can help predict energy consumption, optimize resource allocation, and mitigate quality variations, while responding dynamically to process disturbances or changes in production demand.

¹ BATTwin is a European project developing a multilevel Digital Twin platform for Zero-Defect Manufacturing in Li-ion battery production, funded by the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (grant No. 101137954).

2 Surrogate-assisted optimization framework description and deployment

The proposed framework integrates surrogate modeling into an optimization loop to support fast, adaptive, and sustainability-oriented decision-making in Li-ion battery production. While high-fidelity process simulations remain accurate, they are too computationally demanding for rapid iterative optimization. To overcome this limitation, the surrogate model which is trained on datasets generated from these detailed simulations and from production data, acts as a lightweight approximation capable of predicting system responses at a fraction of the computational cost. This enables the optimization engine to rapidly evaluate numerous scheduling or control alternatives while still preserving a realistic representation of physical process constraints. FIG 1 illustrates how this surrogate-driven architecture operates on the shop floor: production orders feed the optimization module, which relies on surrogate-based predictions to propose candidate schedules or control decisions. These decisions are then validated and refined through selective high-fidelity checks, providing accurate feedback that supports continual correction and learning. The surrogate model is periodically retrained with updated production and validation data, ensuring long-term accuracy, robustness, and adaptability.

FIG. 1 – Surrogate-assisted optimization framework

FIG. 2 – Models' Accuracy

The critical advantage of the surrogate-assisted framework lies in its drastic reduction of computation time. For example, evaluating a single month of production may require up to 27 minutes of simulation time. In contrast, the surrogate model can predict the same system response in a matter of milliseconds, enabling real-time optimization, faster decision updates, and immediate reaction to production disturbances. FIG 2 summarizes the accuracy (using R^2 , which measures how much variance the model explains) of several surrogate models. The neural network achieves the highest accuracy ($R^2 = 87\%$), followed by random forests, making them suitable for real-time use. Linear regression performs poorly on nonlinear dynamics. Overall, this framework enables fast evaluation, adaptive decision-making, and robust solutions for sustainable battery manufacturing.

3 Conclusions and perspectives

The proposed surrogate-assisted optimization framework demonstrates how lightweight predictive models can significantly accelerate decision-making when substituted for a sophisticated digital twin in Li-ion battery production. By combining high-fidelity simulations with fast surrogate predictions, the system enables adaptive and robust decision-making while greatly reducing computational cost. Future work will focus on enabling online updates of the surrogate model, incorporating uncertainty quantification, and extending the optimization toward fully multi-objective and real-time settings.

References

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